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PROCESSING AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED $ZrB_2/SiC/WC$ COMPOSITES

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Abstract

The sintering behavior and mechanical properties of carbon fibre reinforced $ZrB_2/SiC/WC$ composites was investigated. Sintering was carried out between 1800 and 2000°C via hot pressing at 40 MPa. The sample sintered at 1800°C is characterized by higher porosity, while the sample sintered at 2000°C is fully dense but fibres are severely degraded. A temperature of 1900°C allows to obtain 92% dense composite without excessively damaging the fibres.

The microstructure is characterized by the presence of ZrB_2 and solid solutions of W-Si-B. Four-point flexural strength is in the range of 150-200 MPa, while fracture toughness is 4-6 MPam^{0.5}. The sample sintered at 1800°C is characterized by higher K_{Ic} which was attributed to a higher degree of fibre pull-out due to weak fibre/matrix interface. The sample sintered at 2000°C is characterized by very strong fibre/matrix interface due to extensive reaction of the fibre with the surrounding ceramic matrix, leading to brittle fracture behaviour. A temperature of 1900°C was found as the best compromise to maximize strength and avoid brittle fracture. Comparing these results with an un-doped ZrB_2/SiC composite, mechanical properties do not seem to be significantly influenced by the presence of WC, but the presence of WC leads to the formation of a more compact oxide scale, improving the oxidation resistance.

Keywords: Sintering, Mechanical properties, WC, ZrB_2 , carbon fibre

Introduction

Thermal protection systems (TPS) for space vehicles flying at Mach 7 must withstand projected service temperatures up to 2500°C associated to convective heat fluxes up to 15 MWm⁻² and intense mechanical vibrations at launch and re-entry into Earth's atmosphere. The combination of extremely hot temperatures, chemically aggressive environments and rapid heating/cooling is beyond the capabilities of current materials. UHTCMCs (Ultra-High Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites) are a new class of ceramic composites with superior properties in terms of erosion/ablation resistance coupled with superior thermal shock, stability at high temperature and damage tolerance. They are the newest potential candidates for thermal protection systems, able to outperform CMCs¹⁻⁵. UHTCMCs can be fabricated with different approaches, e.g. enriching CMCs with UHTC phases⁶⁷ or impregnating C or SiC preforms with UHTC slurries and closing porosities by CVI or densification^{2,8-10}. A strongly recommended functionality for materials to be used in extreme environments is self-healing capability. For bulk ceramics, self-healing is defined as the ability to partially or completely seal cracks through a thermal treatment, also called crack-healing. The addition of WC was reported to impart a self-healing capability to UHTCs thanks to sintering of the oxidation products (ZrO₂, B-O glasses) developed during high temperature exposure¹¹. Similarly, it was reported that the addition of W into B₂O₃ increases the stability of the protective liquid/glassy layer resulting in higher oxidation resistance for (Zr,W)B₂ compared to nominally pure ZrB₂¹². Binner et al. also reported the increased oxidation resistance of ZrB₂/SiC ceramics with the introduction of WC in environments with low partial pressure of oxygen due to the promotion of passive oxidation of SiC to SiO₂. In this work we investigate the influence of WC addition on the mechanical properties and oxidation resistance of carbon fibre reinforced ZrB₂ – SiC composites and compare it to a reference material without WC.

Materials and methods

Materials

Commercially available powders were used for the preparation of ceramic composite materials: ZrB₂ (H.C. Starck, grade B, Germany, specific surface area 1.0 m²/g, particle size range 0.5-6 µm, impurities (wt.%): 0.25 C, 2 O, 0.25 N, 0.1 Fe, 0.2 Hf), α-SiC (H.C. Starck, Grade UF-25, Germany, specific surface area 23-26 m²/g, D50 0.45 µm Italian retailer: Metalchimica). WC (Materion). Unidirectional high modulus carbon fibres (Granoch Yarn XN80-6K fibres; tensile modulus of 780 GPa and tensile strength 3.4 GPa, 10 µm diameter. Supplier: Angeloni) were used as carbon preforms.

Process

Powder mixtures containing 90 vol% ZrB₂ + 5 vol% SiC + 5 vol% WC were prepared by wet ball milling of the commercial powders and then dried with a rotary evaporator. With these mixtures, aqueous slurries were prepared according to procedures described in¹⁰. Unidirectional carbon fibres were infiltrated with slurries by hand lay-up and stacked in a 0-90° configuration. Hot pressing cycles were then carried out in the range 1800 - 2000°C, using a pressure of 40 MPa for 10 min.

Microstructure

The microstructures were analysed on polished and fractured surfaces by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, Carl Zeiss Sigma NTS GmbH Oberkochen, Germany) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS, INCA Energy 300, Oxford instruments, UK). The starting compositions (e.g. the fibre and matrix volumetric amounts) were estimated in different steps. Before sintering, the green pellet was weighted and the fibre volumetric amount was determined taking into account the fibre areal weight (g/m²) given by the supplier, number of layers and sample area. The matrix amount was then determined as the difference between the total pellet weight and the fibre weight. Theoretical density was calculated using the rule of mixtures.

Mechanical properties

The flexural strength, σ , was evaluated by 4-pt bending strength on 25 x 2.5 x 2 mm (length by width by thickness, respectively) bars, using a semi-articulated steel four-point fixture with a lower span of 20 mm and an upper span of 10 mm using a screw-driven load frame (Zwick/Roell, model Z050), following the guidelines of standard ISO 14704:2016(en). The fracture toughness, K_{Ic} , was evaluated by fracturing chevron notched beams (CNB). The test bars, 25 x 2 x 2.5 mm (length by width by thickness, respectively) were notched with a 0.1 mm-thick diamond saw; the chevron-notch tip depth and average side length were about 0.12 and 0.80 of the bar thickness, respectively. The specimens were fractured using a fully-articulated steel four-point fixture with a lower span of 20 mm and an upper span of 10 mm with a rate of 0.05 mm/min. For each material at least three bars were tested. The "slice model" equation of Munz et al. [19] was used to calculate K_{Ic} .

Oxidation tests

Oxidation tests were carried out on 12 x 2.5 x 2 mm specimens in a bottom-up loading furnace at 1650°C in air for 1 min. The furnace was heated to 1650°C, then the samples were loaded inside the chamber and kept at 1650°C for 1 min. The oxidized specimens were then polished and analysed.

Results and discussion

Three fibre reinforced composites containing $\text{ZrB}_2 + 5\% \text{WC} + 5\% \text{SiC}$ were sintered at different temperatures to find the best hot pressing conditions. Table 1 summarizes hot pressing parameters and the respective physical properties of the sintered pellets.

Table 1. Compositions, sintering cycles, fibre contents and mechanical properties of WC-doped ZrB_2/SiC composites.

Sample	Hot Pressing Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Fibre (vol%)	Density (g/cm^3)	Porosity (vol%)	ZrB_2 grain size (μm)	σ (MPa)	K_{Ic} ($\text{MPam}^{0.5}$)
ZS5	1900	40	3.65	12.9	3.00	198 ± 12	4.7 ± 0.3
ZSW18	1800	39	3.70	20.6	1.26	91 ± 12	4.6 ± 0.3
ZSW19	1900	37	4.51	8.1	1.66	160 ± 25	4.0 ± 0.4
ZSW20	2000	36	4.87	< 1	2.68	96 ± 11	-

Density and porosity are largely affected by the sintering temperature. A residual porosity of 20% is observed after densification at 1800°C , decreasing to 8% when raising the temperature to 1900°C . At 2000°C full density is reached. Microstructural features of the matrix in Fig. 1 are consistent with the density data. Residual pores and a non-perfect cohesion between fibre and matrix is observed in the case of ZSW18. Scattered pockets of bright contrasting particles belonging to WC are observed in the matrix, while the dark and light grey phases belong to SiC and ZrB_2 respectively. On the contrary, for the sample densified at 2000°C , grain growth, coalescence and fibre degradation due to excessive reactivity with the ceramic matrix is observed. Sintering carried out at 1900°C resulted in the most homogeneous microstructure. Solid solutions with W-rich ZrB_2 shells grown onto ZrB_2 cores are well recognizable in the polished surface. This is a very well-known phenomenon due to W diffusion inside the ZrB_2 lattice¹³. Parallel formation of WB phases is also observed, Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Microstructural features of samples ZSW18, ZSW19 and ZSW20. White, grey and dark grey phases represent WC/WB, ZrB_2 and SiC particles respectively. The insert shows the cross section of the fibre (black).

Values of bending strength are negatively affected either by porosities larger than 10% for sintering at 1800°C (~ 90 MPa) or by fibre degradation for sintering at 2000°C (~ 95 MPa). A strength of ~ 160 MPa was obtained for the composite sintered at 1900°C which is slightly lower than the strength of the WC-free composite of ~ 190 MPa. As far as fracture toughness is concerned, the highest value was found for ZSW18 due to weaker fibre/matrix interface which allowed extensive pull-out than ZSW19 and ZSW20 (fig. 2). The latter was difficult to machine because it was very brittle, therefore K_{Ic} values for this specimen are not available. Even in the case of fracture toughness, the addition of WC does not seem to bring significant changes to ZrB_2/SiC composites.

Fig. 2: Cross section of the fractured samples showing progressively lower fibre pull-out extent with the increase of sintering temperature and fibre/matrix strengthening.

Oxidation tests at 1650°C in air were carried out on sample ZSW19 and compared with the WC-free sample, ZS5 (fig. 3). ZS5 is characterized by a fragmented ZrO_2 scale with an external layer of SiO_2 and the pores left by fibres oxidation, while ZSW19 scale is more compact. On closer inspection of the oxide scale (fig. 3), four distinct layers can be observed: 1) an outer silica layer, 2) an intermediate ZrO_2 - SiO_2 - WO_3 scale, with needle-like WO_3 crystals growing together with equiaxed ZrO_2 grains 3) SiC/WC depleted layer with columnar ZrO_2 grains 4) unreacted matrix bulk. The oxide layer of ZSW19 (42 μm) is thinner than ZS5 (85 μm) and more compact, in accordance with previous studies on $ZrB_2/SiC/WC$ ceramics⁹. The presence of the tungsten has been shown to promote the densification of zirconia scales on the top of ZrB_2 via the formation of a ZrO_2 - WO_3 liquid phase during oxidation which might alter the shape and further accelerate the coarsening of ZrO_2 grains¹¹⁴.

Fig. 3: SEM micrographs of the cross section of samples ZS5 and ZSW19 oxidized at 1650°C in air. The dark and light grey phases represent SiO_2 and ZrO_2 respectively, while the white phase is WO_3 . A detail of ZSW19 oxide scale is shown on right.

Conclusions

The addition of WC to ZrB_2 -SiC composites was investigated. A sintering temperature of 1800°C leads to a porous microstructure with weak fibre/matrix interface that favours fibre pull-out but results in lower strength. On the other hand, temperatures above 2000°C lead to excessive reaction between the fibre and the matrix, resulting in brittle fracture and overall lower mechanical properties. A temperature of 1900°C was selected as the best compromise to retain fibre pull-out and maximize strength. The addition of WC does not lead to significant changes in the mechanical properties of ZrB_2/SiC composites, but improves the oxidation resistance at 1650°C by forming a thinner and more compact oxide scale.

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